

Isocoumarins. Part I. Preparation and Cyclisation of 2-Carboxy-4,5-dimethoxyphenylacetaldehyde

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Periodate oxidation of 2-hydroxy-5,6-dimethoxyindan-1-one, obtained from 2-diazo-5,6-dimethoxyindan-1-one, furnishes an excellent yield of 2-carboxy-4,5-dimethoxyphenylacetaldehyde, which has been cyclised most satisfactorily with orthophosphoric acid to 6,7-dimethoxyisocoumarin.

The recent review on isocoumarins by Barry¹ has outlined comprehensively the different methods for the synthesis of a variety of isocoumarins. For the synthesis of isocoumarins, devoid of any substituents in the lactone ring, we evolved a new route¹ involving the preparation of dihydroisocoumarins as intermediates and their transformation to isocoumarins with the aid of NBS. This method has been shown to be the preferred one; but since it involves a number of steps, we have explored possibilities of developing an alternative route which should prove convenient and shorter for preparing isocoumarins in quantities.

Schopf and Kuhne² synthesised the parent compound, isocoumarin, in high yield by cyclisation of *o*-carboxyphenylacetaldehyde, obtained quantitatively by periodate oxidation of 2-hydroxyindan-1-one; the latter was prepared from 2-bromoindan-1-one by acetolysis, followed by hydrolysis of the resulting 2-acetoxyindan-1-one. As this method appears to be the most feasible for our purpose, the synthesis of previously known³ 6,7-dimethoxyisocoumarin (VII), based on the adaptation of these reaction sequences, is reported in the present communication.

β -3,4-Dimethoxyphenylpropionic acid⁴, obtained by the Schwenk-Papa reduction⁵ of 3,4-dimethoxycinnamic acid⁴, was cyclised with polyphosphoric acid to yield the starting material, 5,6-dimethoxyindan-1-one⁶ (I). Interaction of (I) and cupric bromide, a reagent for the bromination of active-hydrogen compounds⁷, afforded 2-bromo-5,6-dimethoxyindan-1-one (II); we found this procedure more expeditious than the direct bromination method of Barltrop⁸. All our attempts to convert the bromo compound (II) into 2-acetoxy-5,6-dimethoxyindan-1-one (III), however, proved unsuccessful. Acetolysis with potassium acetate or silver acetate under a variety of conditions afforded unchanged starting material with traces of (III), the maximum yield being 10%, when potassium

1. *Chem. Rev.*, 1964, **64**, 229, and the references cited therein.
2. *Chem. Ber.*, 1950, **83**, 390.
3. Kamal *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 3375; Srivastava and Chaudhury, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1962, **27**, 4337.
4. Johnson and Glenn, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, **71**, 1092.
5. *J. Org. Chem.*, 1942, **7**, 587.
6. Koo, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 1891.
7. Fort, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1962, **26**, 785.
8. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 958.

acetate in glacial acetic acid was used at 120° for 2 hours. Again, treatment of 5,6-dimethoxyindan-1-one (I) with lead tetra-acetate, according to the literature method⁹ for acetoxylation of indan-1-one, did not furnish (III), but provided only intractable products. The acetoxyindanone (III) was ultimately obtained in excellent yield by an altogether different route. Treatment of the sodium salt of 5,6-dimethoxy-2-oximinoindan-1-one¹⁰ with ammonia and sodium hypochlorite¹¹ afforded 2-diazo-5,6-dimethoxyindan-1-one (V) in 96.7% yield. The conditions for this preparation are critical and a slight change of the hypochlorite concentration or of temperature lowers the yield. Interaction with acetic acid converted the diazoketone (V) to 2-acetoxy-5,6-dimethoxyindan-1-one (III) (80%).

Deacetylation of (III) with potassium carbonate in methanol at 0° under N₂ atmosphere provided 2-hydroxy-5,6-dimethoxyindan-1-one (IV) (63.8%) which was oxidised with periodic acid to afford a 90% yield of 2-carboxy-4,5-dimethoxyphenylacetaldehyde (VI). Cyclisation of the acid aldehyde (VI) to 6,7-dimethoxyisocoumarin³ (VII) (85%) was most successfully accomplished by means of hot orthophosphoric acid which served as a suitable solvent for the reaction. Schopf and Kuhne² used boiling dilute hydrochloric acid for cyclisation of *o*-carboxyphenylacetaldehyde to isocoumarin, but the use of the mineral acid for cyclising (VI) did not prove satisfactory. Synthesis of other isocoumarins by this route is in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL

3,4-Dimethoxyphenylpropionic Acid.—Adopting the general procedure⁵ for the Schwenk-Papa reduction, 3,4-dimethoxycinnamic acid⁴ (35 g.) in 10% NaOH solution (1050 ml) was reduced with Raney Ni-Al alloy (105 g.) to yield the propionic acid which was crystallised from water or ethyl acetate-light petroleum (32 g., 91%), m.p. 102° (lit.³ m.p. 102°).

Perkin and Robinson¹⁰ used Na-Hg for reduction, whereas others^{4,12} employed catalytic hydrogenation.

5,6-Dimethoxyindan-1-one (I).—The literature method⁶ involving the use of commercial PPA was modified as follows: The preceding acid (10 g.) was added in one lot with stirring

*All m.p.s are uncorrected. Light petroleum used had b.p. 60-80°. Extracts with organic solvents dried with Na₂SO₄.

9. Marvel and Hinman, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 5435.

10. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, **91**, 1073.

11. Forster, *ibid.*, 1915, **107**, 280.

12. Horning *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 5826.

to PPA [from P_2O_5 (50 g.) + H_3PO_4 (d 1.75, 30 ml)] at 90° when the temperature rose to 100° , which was maintained for 6 min. It was poured in ice, extracted with ethyl acetate, and the extract worked up in the usual way. Crystallisation from ethyl acetate-light petroleum afforded pure ketone (I) in colorless, rectangular prisms (6.6 g., 72.5%), m.p. $121-22^\circ$ (lit.⁶ m.p. $117-19^\circ$).

5,6-Dimethoxy-2-oximinoindan-1-one was obtained in a manner analogous to the method of Cava *et al.*¹³ for the preparation of 2-oximinoindan-1-one. Isoamyl nitrite (10 ml) was added to a stirred solution of (I) (13.7 g.) in methyl cellosolve (60 ml) and HCl (conc., 20 ml) when a solid began to separate within 4 min. After $\frac{1}{2}$ hr., the mixture was poured on cold water, the product filtered, and washed well with water and dilute ethanol. Crystallisation from glacial acetic acid furnished the oximino compound (12.2 g., 77.4%) in yellow needles, m.p. 240° (decomp.) [lit.¹⁰ m.p. 240° (decomp.)].

2-Diazo-5,6-dimethoxyindan-1-one (V).—A solution of the preceding compound (13.72 g.) in NaOH (0.32*N*, 100 ml) was stirred and cooled to -2° , when after 10 min. a portion of the sodium salt separated. 15*N*- NH_4OH (4 ml) was added, followed by dropwise addition of NaOCl solution (5.364%, 99 ml) over a period of 25 min., the temperature being maintained throughout at -2° . The reaction mixture was held at this temperature for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. after the addition was complete. The ice bath was then removed and stirring continued for 35 min. at $12-15^\circ$ when the diazo compound was precipitated. The reaction mixture, which was stirred for a further period of $1\frac{1}{2}$ hr, gradually attained the room temperature (32°); the diazo compound was filtered, washed well with water, and dried in an exiccator. It weighed 13 g. (96.7%), m.p. $150-51^\circ$ (decomp.), and was used for the next step without further purification. A sample, crystallised from ethyl acetate-light petroleum, furnished a specimen of pure compound (V) as brown needles, m.p. 153° (decomp.). (Found: C, 60.8; H, 4.7; N, 13.0 $C_{11}H_{10}O_3N_2$ requires C, 60.5; H, 4.5; N, 12.8%). This experiment, when performed with 5.3% NaOCl, the yield of the diazo compound dropped to 12.5 g.

2-Acetoxy-5,6-dimethoxyindan-1-one (III).—The diazoketone (V) (3 g.) was added portionwise to glacial acetic acid (18 ml) when N_2 evolved copiously and a clear solution was obtained. Next day, it was heated on a water bath for 15 min., diluted with water (90 ml), and extracted with ethyl acetate. The extract was washed with aqueous sodium bicarbonate and water and dried. Evaporation of the solvent left a solid residue which was crystallised from water to afford pure (III) in off-white needles (2.74 g., 80.1%), m.p. $142-43^\circ$. (Found: C, 62.6; H, 5.3. $C_{13}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 62.4; H, 5.6%). It reduced Fehling's solution on heating.

Its 2,4-DNP, prepared by adopting Shine's method¹⁴, was crystallised from dioxane in crimson needles, m.p. 260° (decomp.). (Found: N, 13.1. $C_{19}H_{18}O_8N_4$ requires N, 13.02%).

2-Hydroxy-5,6-dimethoxyindan-1-one (IV).—To a solution of the foregoing compound (2 g.) in methanol (20 ml) was added K_2CO_3 (1.4 g. in 20 ml water) under N_2 atmosphere and kept in the frigidaire overnight. It was diluted with cold water (200 ml), thoroughly extracted with chloroform, and the dried extract concentrated and percolated through a column of Brockmann's alumina, using chloroform as the eluent. Evaporation of the

13. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 2257.

14. *J. Org. Chem.*, 1959, **24**, 252.

solvent furnished a crystalline residue which was recrystallised from chloroform-light petroleum in rectangular prisms (1.06 g., 63.8%), m.p. 151-52°. (Found: C, 63.2; H, 5.4. $C_{11}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 63.46; H, 5.7%). It readily reduced Fehling's solution in cold and formed a blue precipitate with baryta, a characteristic test¹⁵ for cyclic ketols.

Its 2,4-*DNP*, prepared by following Shine's method¹⁴, was crystallised from dioxane in deep maroon needles, m.p. 259-60° (decomp.). (Found: N, 14.6. $C_{17}H_{16}O_7N_4$ requires N, 14.4%).

2-Carboxy-4,5-dimethoxyphenylacetaldehyde (VI).—The preceding ketol (1g.) in water (30 ml) was heated on a water bath when a clear solution was obtained. It was cooled to 0° and to it was added an ice-cooled solution of HIO_4 (1.84 g. in 21 ml water) and after 2 min., a crystalline material started separating. The reaction mixture was kept at 0° for 10 min. and then at the room temperature for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. The crystals were collected, washed well with ice-cold water, and recrystallised from ethanol in prisms (0.97 g., 90%), m.p. 163-67°. (Found: C, 60.1; H, 5.1. $C_{11}H_{12}O_5$ requires C, 58.9; H, 5.3%).

Its 2,4-*DNP*, prepared as usual, was obtained in golden yellow needles (from diglyme), m.p. 214-15°. (Found: N, 14.0. $C_{17}H_{16}O_8N_4$ requires N, 13.8%).

6,7-Dimethoxyisocoumarin (VII).—The above acid-aldehyde (0.5 g.) and H_3PO_4 (*d* 1.75, 2 ml) was heated on a water bath for 10 min. when a clear pink solution resulted. It was poured on ice, extracted well with ethyl acetate, the extract was washed with aqueous sodium bicarbonate and water, and dried. Evaporation of the solvent left a crystalline residue which was sublimed under partial vacuum. The sublimate, on crystallisation from ethyl acetate-light petroleum, afforded pure (VII) as needles (0.4 g., 85%), m.p. 121-22°, undepressed on admixture with an authentic specimen, m.p. 122-23°, prepared by Srivastava and Chaudhury³, following a different route.

2-Bromo-5,6-dimethoxyindan-1-one (II).—The indanone (I) (5 g.) in methanol (30 ml) was treated with a solution of cupric bromide (12.3 g.) and KBr (7.3 g.) in water (30 ml) and refluxed on a water bath for 1 hr. It was cooled and the precipitated solid collected, washed with a saturated KBr solution, followed by water, and dried in an exiccator. Crystallisation from methanol afforded pure (II) in pale yellow needles (4.0 g., 57%), m.p. 158° (lit.⁸ m.p. 157°).